

Development of irrigated agriculture in Angola

Effects on the downstream Okavango Delta

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The Okavango Delta

- situated in a desert
- all water evaporates
- a biodiversity hotspot

How much current irrigation?

- classification of satellite images

A

B

C

- Desert, bare land, sand
- Short grass, dry vegetation
- Grassland, medium and dense
- Irrigated agriculture
- Forest
- Surface water, river
- Housing, bare land

How big is the potential for irrigated agriculture?

Satellite based radar images used for criteria

Agriculture defined from the parameters:

- Horizontal distance
- Vertical distance
- Slope of landscape

How is the river flow affected if the full potential for agriculture is used?

- The flow decreases with with 35% in the wet season
- The river dries out in the dry season

What is the impacts on the Okavango Delta?

- The depth to groundwater increases
- The delta decrease in size

How big is the impacts on the Okavango Delta nature?

- Increased agriculture decrease the wet ecoregions
- The dry area increase in size

Annual benefits from agriculture = 800 million US\$

Value of 1m³ water = 0.15 US\$

Tourism benefits > 1 billion US\$